

A study to Assess the Effectiveness of Information Booklet Regarding Stress Management among English Medium Students in Selected High Schools at Bangalor

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Abstract:- The research approach used was an evaluate research approach. The research design selected for the study was pre experimental one group pre and post test research design. The independent variable of the study was the information booklet on stress management. The dependent variables in the study undertaken were the scores on the knowledge test. The informational booklet was developed on the basis of review research and non-research literature related to stress among high school children's, effectiveness of stress, knowledge, prevention and control of stress, teaching strategies, development and evaluation of the information booklet. The booklet was prepared in English. It was validated by 5 experts out of which two were from the field of psychiatrics, two were from the field of psychiatric nursing and one were from the field of education.

The data obtained were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics, in terms of frequencies, percentages, mean, mode, SD, and "t" value.

Sample characteristic revealed that 46% of respondents were in age group of 14-15, 56% were females, 70% were days scholars, 26% were last born child, 58% of the respondents father education was professional degree, 62% were studying 8th standard, 30% of the respondents were reported the exposure to literature on stress as "rarely". The study findings revealed significant gain in knowledge and attitude scores after the administration of the information booklet.

Keywords:- Assess, Stress, English medium school, English medium high school students, Knowledge, Effectiveness, Information booklet.

I. INTRODUCTION

School is your child's "job". It's where he spends most of his time. His work is scored and measured, and compares himself with others every day. Academic stress and social pressure are two big causes of anxiety for school-age children. Meeting parents and teachers high expectations for school can be stressful.

Stress levels among children have been going up dangerously, for, regardless of their ability, they are expected to excel in all areas in life, is they academic or cultural activities. Not all children can cope with such high levels of expectation and parents do not seem to realise or accept that their children are under severe pressure".

A sudden change in a child's behavior may be related to stress. Caregivers can talk with the parents about what is going on in the home.²

As educational requirements get more stringent in all levels of education. Students everywhere experiences considerable school stress. Based on these factors the investigators felt the need to make the children more flexible, realistic and assured of their own inner resources. And when they faced with stressors, they have to show the capacity to recover quickly from temporary collapse or defend against problem.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

A study to assess the effectiveness of information booklet regarding stress management among English medium students in selected high schools at Bangalore.

III. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To assess the pre test knowledge regarding the stress management among English medium high school students.
- To develop an information booklet on stress among English medium high school students.
- To assess the post test knowledge regarding the stress management among English medium high school students.
- To evaluate the effectiveness of information booklet on stress management.
- To find out the association between knowledge's regarding stress management with selected demographic variables.

IV. RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

- **H₁:** -The mean post test knowledge score of the high school students completing the information booklet will be significantly higher than the mean pre test knowledge score at a 0.05 level of significance as measured on knowledge test.
- **H₂:** -There will be significant association between pre test and post test score of the students with selected demographic variables.

V. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

It presents logically constructed concepts to provide general relationship between the concepts of the research study, without using single existing theory. Conceptual frameworks are usually constructed by using researchers.

The conceptual framework in nursing research can help to provide a clear and concise idea of knowledge in the area. The modified conceptual framework for the present study is based on Imogene Kings Goal Attainment theory (1981). This theory focuses on the interpersonal relationship between client and nurses. The interaction is influenced by the perception and leads to mutual goal setting which are to be achieved by the nurse and the client. In the study the interaction takes place between the investigator and students.

- **Perception:** Perception is in each person a representation of reality. The element of perception are the importing of energy from the environment and organizing it by information, transferring energy, processing information, storing information and expressing in the form of overt behaviors. In the present study the investigator perceive the need to improve knowledge regarding stress management among English medium high school students. The school students perceive the need to learn about stress management.
- **Judgment:** Judgment is a set of behaviors expected of person occupying a position in a social system, rules that define right and obligation in opposition. It is a relationship between one or more individual interacting in a specific situation for a purpose. The investigator decided to enhance the knowledge regarding stress management among English medium high school students through information booklet. The students would decide to utilize the information booklet to increase their knowledge on stress management.

- **Action:** Action is the physical and mental activity to achieve the goal what individual perceive. The investigator prepares structured interview schedule and information booklet on stress management.
- **Reaction:** Reaction is not specifically defined but might be considered to be included in the sequence of behaviors described in action and also referred as the process where teachers transform information. In the present study the investigator and students are together setting mutual goal on learning more regarding stress management.
- **Interaction:** Interaction is defined as process of perception and communication between person and environment, between person and person represented by verbal and non verbal behaviors that are goal directed. The investigator conducts the pretest by using structured interview schedule and information booklet to English medium high school students. The students participate in the pretest and utilize the information booklet on stress management.
- **Transaction:** Transaction is defined as observable behavior of human being interaction with the environment, when transaction of knowledge regarding stress management is enhanced to attain the goal. Between teachers and students is done and goals are attained. In this stage investigator reassess the knowledge of students regarding stress management by conducting posttest.

The positive outcome indicates the improvement of knowledge on stress management which shows the effectiveness of information booklet on stress management among English medium high school students and no gain of knowledge score indicates inadequate knowledge regarding stress management where the students need to be reinforced for further planning for further knowledge enforcement.

FIG 1: CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK BASED ON GOAL ATTAINMENT THEORY

VI. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

• **Research Approach:** The research approach adopted for this study is a evaluate research approach. This study aims at assessing the knowledge regarding stress management

to school students at selected English medium high schools.

• **Research Design:** The research design used for this study was pre experimental one group pre and post test research design.

Study Group	Pre-Test	Intervention	Post-Test
	(Administration of structured knowledge questionnaire)	(Administration of information booklet)	(Administration of structured knowledge questionnaire)
High school Students	O ₁	X	O ₂

• **Population:** Target populations for present study comprised of 173 high school students in Ragavendra English High School.

• **Sample:** In the present study the sample consisted of 50 high school students in Ragavendra English High School, Bangalore

• **Sampling Technique:** The sample technique will be adapted for the study is simple random sampling technique.

• **Description of the tool:** The tool for the data collection consists of two sections: -

• **Section A: Socio-demographic variables**

It deals with demographic variables which include age, gender, place of residence, standard of studying, parents educational status, type of family, how often you read literature related to stress, students felt stress by them self.

• **Section B: Knowledge regarding stress management:**

This part consists of 24 multiple choice questions which includes the following selected aspects on stress management. The multiple choice question with response given. One score was given to each correct answer and the possible range of score was from 0-24. The answer key is presented in appendix.

- General information regarding stress management
- Knowledge on stress
- Technique of relieving stress
- Causes of stress
- Symptoms of stress
- Development of Self Instructional Module (SIM)

The Module was prepared on the basis of information obtained during extensive literature. The finalized content was in English and prepared as a Information Booklet.

VII. RESULTS

• **Objective 1: To assess the pre-test knowledge regarding the stress management among English medium high school students.**

N = 50			
	Knowledge level	Frequency	%
a.	Inadequate knowledge	25	50.0
b.	Moderate knowledge	25	50.0
c.	Adequate knowledge	0	0.0
Total		50	100.0

Table 1: Pretest knowledge level on stress management

Table 12 depicts that 50% of the students had inadequate knowledge and 50% had moderate knowledge in the pretest.

Fig. 12: Pre test knowledge level on stress management

N = 50

Sl. No.	Knowledge aspects	No. of Items	Max Score	Mean	Mean %	Median	SD
1.	Overall	24	24	12.46	51.91	12.5	1.528

Table 2: Overall analysis of pre-test knowledge scores on stress management

Table 13 depicts that the overall mean knowledge scores of respondents were found to be 19.22 (54.91%) with standard deviation 2.435 indicates moderate knowledge on stress management

• **Objective 2: To assess the post test knowledge regarding the stress management among English medium high school students.**

N = 50

Knowledge level		Frequency	%
a.	Inadequate knowledge	0	0.0
b.	Moderate knowledge	35	70.0
c.	Adequate knowledge	15	30.0
Total		50	100

Table 2: Post test knowledge level on stress management

Table 14 depicts that 30% of the respondents had adequate knowledge and 70% had moderate knowledge regarding stress management.

Fig 14: Post test knowledge level on stress management

N = 50

Sl. No.	Knowledge aspects	No. of Items	Max Score	Mean	Mean %	Median	SD
1.	Overall	24	24	16.8	70	16.5	2.703

Table 15: Overall analysis of post-test knowledge scores on stress management

Table 15 depicts that the overall mean knowledge scores of respondents were found to be 25.18 (71.94%) with standard deviation 3.740 shows improvement in the knowledge on stress management

• **Objective 3: To find out the association between knowledge's regarding stress management with selected demographic variables.**

N= 50

Variables	Below Median	Median and above	Chi square	Df	P value (0.05)	Inference
1. Age in years						
a. 13-14 years	2	3	19.335	3	0.000	S
b. 14-15 years	19	4				
c. 15-16 years	2	13				
d. 16 years above	2	5				
2. Gender						
a. Male	9	13	1.299	1	0.254	NS
b. Female	16	12				
3. Area of residence						
a. Days scholars	16	19	0.857	1	0.355	NS
b. Hostellers	9	6				
4. Birth order						
a. Only one child	3	8	6.306	5	0.278	NS
b. First born	6	4				
c. Middle born	5	3				
d. Last born	7	5				
e. Twins	1	4				
f. Any other	3	1				
5. Type of family						
a. Joint	0	0	-	-	-	-
b. Nuclear	25	25	7.032	6	0.212	NS
6. Educational status of father						
a. Professional degree (MA, MSC)	15	14	3.987	3	0.263	NS
b. Basic degree (BA, BSC)	5	2				
c. Schooling (primary school, high school)	4	4				
d. Illiterate	1	5				
7. Standard of studying						
a. 8 th std	16	15	2.651	3	0.449	NS
b. 9 th std	6	3				
c. 10 th std	2	5				
8. How often you read literature related stress						
a. Health magazine, news paper	4	4	0.467	3	0.926	NS
b. Very often	7	8				
c. Rarely	7	8				
d. Never	7	5				
9. Students felt stress by them self						
a. no	18	15	0.802	1	0.370	S
b. yes	7	10				

Table 17: Association of post test knowledge scores with the demographic variables

The table 17 shows χ^2 value computed between the knowledge levels on stress management with selected demographic variables. Variables such as gender, area of residence, birth order, type of family, Standard of studying, educational status of father, how often you read literature related to stress were not significant at 0.05 levels. Thus the hypothesis stated there will be significant association between knowledge level on stress management with variables such as age, felt stress by them self were significant.

VIII. CONCLUSION

- Overall mean knowledge scores of respondents before SIM is found to be 54.91% and after SIM is 71.94%.
- Information booklet was effective in improving the knowledge of English medium high school students regarding stress management
- The study indicates, association between demographic variables & knowledge score on stress management there exists a significant associated between pretest knowledge score on stress management among English medium high school students & selected demographic variable

RECOMMENDATIONS

- A similar study may be replicated by taking a large sample of English medium high school students.
- A similar study can be replicated on a sample with English medium prep school students.
- A similar study may be conducted with different method of teaching program.
- A comparative study can be between both high schools and upper primary school students
- A similar study can be done with different aspects of practice
- A similar study can be conducted between two schools of high school students.

REFERENCES

- [1.] URL: <http://kalyan-city.blogspot.in/2011/03/what-is-stress-meaning-definition>.
- [2.] Daniel N. Brooks. Specific Stressors and the Specific Stress Symptoms They Eict in School- Age Children.
- [3.] Hammerfald K, Grau M, et al. Persistent effects of cognitive-behavioral stress Management on cortisol responses to acute stress in healthy subjects-A randomized controlled trial. Psych neuroendocrinology. 2005 Sep 22; epub ahead of print.
- [4.] Honig, A. S. (1986). Stress and Coping in Children. In J. McCracken (Ed.), Reducing Stress in children's Lives.
- [5.] Sreevani R.A Guide to Mental Health Nursing and psychiatric Nursing. 2nd Ed. New Delhi, Jaypee publications; 2008,p 210-6.
- [6.] High School Students Struggle with Stress, Depression By elizabeth hopper Special to the Planet Friday August 26, 2005.
- [7.] Focus on Education. SG KE TOI India - English Number 3 as medium of instruction. Times of India. Nov 22, 2007.
- [8.] Peach, larry. A study concerning stress among high school students in selected rural schools. Education resources and information center. 2012. P 12.
- [9.] Lone Aaliya, Mir Zaffar Iqbal. Mental health of adolescents with special reference to Kashmir, Indian journal of health and wellbeing 458-459.
- [10.] Minami Yosuke, Maruyama Tomohiro, Miyazaki Shingo et al. Stress of 461 junior high school students and the factors. Shakai to Igaku Jisshu. Heisei 14 Nendo. Eiseigaku, Kosshu Eiseigaku Jiyu Kenkyu Hokokusho. 2004: 103-108.
- [11.] Haugland S, Wold B. The role of physical activity in the relationship between school- lated stress and adolescent health complaints. Research quarterly for exercise and spot. 2003 jun. P 74(2):127-35.
- [12.] Shields N. Stress, active coping, and academic performance among persisting and non persisting students. Journal of Applied Bio behavioral Research. 2001; 6:65-81.
- [13.] Jennifer Warner, Teen Stress at Home Lingers in School, WebMD Health News, Reviewed by Louise Chang, MD, May 15, 2008, for more information. Visit URL: <http://www.medicinenet.com>
- [14.] Kader P. Nursing Research. 2nd Ed. Palgrave Macmillan. New York; 2006.
- [15.] John D. Moulds. Stress manifestation in high school students: An Australian sample. Wiley Periodicals, Inc. Psychol Schs, 2003:40 391-402. URL: <http://www.interscience.wiley.com/journal>.
- [16.] Tajularipin Sulaiman, Aminuddin Hassan. The Level of Stress among Students in Urban and Rural Secondary Schools in Malaysia. European Journal of Social Sciences –Volume-10, November 2 (2009).